

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

UDC 811.111

NON-NORMATIVE VOCABULARY

Kismetova G.N.,*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University***Koblandiyeva M.B.***Master's student of the philological faculty,
Makhambet Utemisov West Kazakhstan University*

Abstract

The article examines the relationship between literary, colloquial, neutral and non-normative vocabulary.

Keywords: literary, colloquial, neutral and non-normative vocabulary, lexical dialectisms, vulgarism, slang.

The social changes taking place in society are reflected in the language and affect not only the vocabulary, but also the culture of communication as a whole. The process of democratisation of the literary language has become manifest in the expansion of the ways and forms of expression, in the use of expressive words and expressions.

As A. Bolganbaev points out in spoken speech the expression or stylistic function of grammatical structures have significant changes and peculiarities compared to writing styles. The stylistic features of spoken speech are built on the style that differs from the norm of the written literary language, which is essentially non-normative vocabulary [1].

Non-normative is a particular segment of vocabulary that includes vulgar, rude and obscene swear words, expressing in most cases a spontaneous reaction to an unpleasant and unexpected situation [2].

The layer of profanity, includes lexical dialectisms, vulgarisms and slang units.

Lexical dialectisms are linguistic features characteristic of territorial dialects, which are distinguished in the flow of literary speech as deviations from the norm [3, p. 133].

Vulgarism is a term attached to a certain group of words and phrases, united by one leading feature, namely the degree of rudeness, which borders on obscenity [4, p. 101]. These are well-known swearwords such as *son of a bitch, to hell, damn, bloody*, etc. in English. The purpose is to show anger, irritation, violent emotions. "True" vulgarisms denote such objects, processes and actions that are never mentioned in decent conversation, although in the field of medicine many of them have scientific terms [3, p. 68].

Slang is a polysemous term, which, firstly, denotes the vocabulary available only to certain social

groups and closed to the understanding of other speakers, and secondly, it represents a set of colloquial vocabulary reflecting a roughly-familiar, humorous attitude to the subject of speech [5, p. 461].

However, distinguishing lexical layers as literary, colloquial and non-normative is not enough to correlate a lexical unit with one or another lexical layer. The study of the level of stylistic colouring of vocabulary requires some kind of standard equation that would allow one to correlate a lexical unit with a particular lexical layer. Such a benchmark is the neutral lexicon, which such linguists as I. Halperin, C. Fries, X. Alexander and others do not consider as a necessary component in the classification.

The study of lexical stylistic stratification implies the identification of lexical strata with different stylistic functions. However, it is impossible to establish clear boundaries of these strata, to "shelve" all the lexical wealth of the language and state that one lexeme is always official, another is unofficial, and the third is colloquial [6].

There is no more mobile layer in a language than the lexicon. When we speak of "mobility" we mean the relatively rapid rate of change in the lexical composition of a language and its replenishment with new words or new meanings of already existing words, acquiring different stylistic coloration. This does not mean that the vocabulary cannot be systematically studied at all, but it is necessary to take into account the interaction of lexical layers, the penetration of lexemes from one layer to another [7, p. 39].

For this reason, we are based on the classification of the linguist C. Friese. The lexical layers have been depicted as intersecting circles, which gives an idea of the interaction of these layers (see schema №1).

"X" - formal, literary English;

"U" - colloquial, informal English of cultivated people;

"Z" - illiterate, uneducated English;

b, c, e - represent the overlapping of the three types;

c - that which is common to all three;

b - that which is common to formal and colloquial;

e - that which is common to colloquial and illiterate;

a, d, f, represent the portions peculiar to that set of language habits.

Our circle of interest lies primarily in the sphere Z, in which Friese singles out zones c, e, f, as if to emphasise the permeability and blurring of the boundaries of all three spheres, in other words, the openness of these structures [8, p. 16].

Thus, the three social varieties of speech, with certain variations and stylistic functions, are summarised as terms:

1. literary and colloquial speech;
2. Familiar and colloquial speech;
3. colloquialism.

The most affected by profanity is the colloquial vocabulary, for the reason that it is as close as possible to the former in terms of the stylistic colouring of words. The boundaries between these layers are so blurred that one can often observe a rapid transition from the non-normative layer to the colloquial one and vice versa. In the vocabulary of colloquial speech extra-literary slang words are used as expressive inclusions; they are most common in the speech of young people, as words of this kind are characterized by high expressiveness, coloring of familiarity and inferiority [9, p. 28]. The colloquial layer is a kind of "transition point" between the neutral and non-normative layers. The mixing of different connotations can be observed within a single lexical unit that has several meanings. Thus, the word *knockout* is, first of all, a sports term; besides, it has a neutral meaning "knocking down a blow", a colloquial meaning "outstanding person" and a non-normative meaning "drug". The semantic reinterpretation of a lexical unit automatically changes its stylistic coloring: from literary to profane.

The interaction of the non-normative layer with the neutral lexicon consists in using the latter to replen-

ish the non-normative vocabulary through semantic reinterpretation of neutral words. As a result, a neutral lexical unit gets a new meaning, stylistically reduced and emotionally colored. For example, the English word *frog* - "stupid person" - has become part of the profanity.

The reason for the penetration of profanity into the book and other strata was its active use in films, books, journalism, the media, the main purpose of which is to transmit cultural values to the speakers of a particular national language. As a result, there is a process of blurring the boundaries between language subsystems [10, p. 29]. In addition, this process can be explained by some psychological reasons. Nowadays, there is a linguistic fashion in many languages, which allows and encourages familiarity and insolence characteristic of profanity. The vivid emotional and expressive colouring of this vocabulary appeals to many segments of the population, especially young people.

Studies show that the greatest influx of abusive words into people's speech occurs during social and political upheavals - wars, revolts, revolutions, etc., when speakers have a desire to move away from the old canons and replace them with something new [11, p. 82].

Thus, the stylistic classification is based on four lexical strata: neutral, literary, colloquial and non-normative. The neutral layer, common to all the others, is the basis of the classification, in comparison with which there is a contrast between the other lexical layers: literary, colloquial and non-normative. All four layers are depicted as circles, their interaction is indicated by overlapping circles, and the vagueness of the boundaries between them and the free transition of lexical units from one subsystem to another is represented by arrows (see schema №2):

A study of the key lexical strata, their attributes and interactions leads to the following conclusions. Four lexical layers underlie the stylistic classification, i.e. literary, colloquial, neutral and non-normative. The classification is based on the neutral style, which is a kind of benchmark, the comparison with which allows us to correlate a lexeme with one or another lexical layer. The lexical layers are schematically arranged into intersecting circles connected by arrows, which served to denote the vagueness of the borders between them and their continuous interaction. The process of interaction of the non-normative lexical layer with other lexical layers is contradictory. On the one hand, the profanity replenishes its vocabulary using the vocabulary of these layers. On the other hand, it actively penetrates into these layers and is used by many speakers.

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